

DEVELOPING THE NEXT GENERATION OF POLYETHYLENE BASED SINGLE POLYMER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Self-reinforced single polymer composites, where both the reinforcing fibre and matrix are both polymeric and usually the same polymer, offer new opportunities to manufacturers. They can help to confront increasing costs arising from emerging environmental constraints which focus on issues such as recyclability and the greater emphasis on the reduction in material and energy consumption during the life cycle of a product. The technical challenge is to extend the considerable advantages in respect of mechanical properties that can be achieved in small cross section, such as highly oriented fibres, to a composite sheet with all the associated material issues of matrix type, fibre properties, compatibility between fibre and matrix and arrangement of the reinforcement (e.g. weave style) Of equal importance is the choice of material type depending on the end use application, and in particular can it be thermoformed. In this paper we present some recent work where we have investigated these issues for self reinforced polyethylene composites.

Keywords: polymer/polymer composites: thermoforming: polyethylene: thermoplastics: hot compaction

INTRODUCTION

Research work at Leeds over the last 20 years has seen the development of a new type of composite material, termed all polymer, or single polymer, composite. The process developed at Leeds, termed hot compaction, starts from an assembly of oriented, high modulus, melt spun fibres or tapes. Research showed that if this assembly was taken to a critical temperature, while held under a moderate pressure, it was possible to melt a fraction of the surface of each oriented element, which on cooling recrystallised to form the matrix of the single polymer composite. The first studies, in 1989, were carried out on melt spun PE fibres produced commercially by SNIA-FIBRE under the trade name TENFOR. These fibres are identical to those produced subsequently by Hoechst Celanese under the trade name CERTRAN which are the focus of the current research presented in this paper.

The term 'single polymer composites' was first coined by Capiati and Porter [1] who utilised the difference between the melting points of highly oriented gel spun polyethylene (PE) fibres and isotropic PE to embed a PE filament in a block of high density polyethylene. For this model structure high interfacial shear strengths were observed which were attributed to the development of an epitaxially crystallised trans crystalline layer on the

fibre surface. Subsequently, several other methods have been reported to make such polymer/polymer composites including film stacking [2-3] powder impregnation [4-5] pressure controlled melting [6] and bicomponent fibres [7-8].

Our initial study [9] used unidirectional arrays of PE fibres in order to establish the critical processing conditions. The key was to choose a temperature that would melt a sufficient fraction of the original fibres to produce a matrix phase to consolidate the composite, without losing too much of the original properties. An important aspect was the collaboration with David Bassett and Robert Olley at the University of Reading, whose morphological studies proved crucial in establishing the optimum processing conditions [10]. Figure 1a shows a typical scanning electron microscope picture of what is considered an ‘optimum’ sample. The micrograph clearly shows a structure where the original oriented fibres are surrounded by a matrix of the melted and recrystallised material. Figure 1b is an etched longitudinal section showing that, as in the original studies of Capiati and Porter, there is epitaxial recrystallisation of the matrix phase onto the original fibres

Figure 1: Etched micrographs from unidirectional arranged PE fibres:
a) SEM picture of a transverse section of compacted fibres b) TEM picture of an interstitial lamellar region and its junction with adjacent fibres

A critical advantage of the hot compaction process is that the ‘matrix’ is exactly the same polymer as the reinforcement, giving excellent compatibility and adhesion between the two components.

Subsequent research used woven arrays of oriented elements [11], to give a final composite with more balanced mechanical properties. In recent studies [12], the original hot compaction concept has been widened to use interleaved films of usually the same polymer between the woven layers during the manufacturing process. This has the advantage of

locating more 'matrix' material in the interlayer region, which is often a weakness in these materials and can be crucial for successful thermoforming.

Commercialisation of the hot compaction technology was achieved using woven polypropylene tapes, rather than the high modulus PE fibres used for all the original scientific studies. This was due to the oriented PP raw material being both readily available (for carpet and geotextile applications) and cost effective. The commercial material (CurvTM) has most successfully been used for suitcases by Samsonite (the 'X-Lite range) utilizing the lightweight and impact strength of single polypropylene composites. However, some applications, for instance in the automotive sector, require higher stiffness and strength, hence the continuing interest in single polymer composites based on high modulus melt spun PE fibres.

The work presented in this paper forms part of the recent FuturePlas project. The aim of this project was to develop and exploit new polymer/polymer composite materials (<http://www.futureplas.com/>). This project was funded by the UK Technology Strategy Board under the priority area of Design and Manufacture of Sustainable Products and had four main aims: to reduce of the amount of plastic used to make a component by 30%: to reduce the component weight by 30%: to improve the recyclability of reinforced plastics: and to improve the design flexibility of self-reinforced plastics. The project involved eight UK partners comprising the whole supply chain: the project leaders, NetComposites: James Dewhurst who are specialty weavers: Exel Composites UK who specialise in pultrusion: McKecknie Plastics who are speciality injection moulders: JSP, Bentley Motors Limited and Visteon who are potential end users: and the academic partners, University of Leeds. While a number of polymers, and processes, were studied as part of the FuturePlas programme, in this paper we will concentrate on the studies of melt spun polyethylene based materials made by the hot compaction process

The work is presented in three sections: a study of the effect of weave style on single polyethylene composite sheet mechanical properties: establishing thermoforming parameters using a model hemispherical mould: thermoforming and testing of a demonstrator component.

THE EFFECTS OF WEAVE STYLE

Two weave styles were investigated: a plain weave style as utilised in previous studies [13] and a special weave style produced by James Dewhurst, comprising unidirectional, straight, Certran PE multifilaments with a fine PET monofilament carrier. The aim was to investigate whether a better transfer of fibre properties into the final composite sheet could be achieved with the unidirectional cloth, which had much reduced fibre crimp compared to the standard plain weave previously studied [11]. For details of the Certran fibres see [13].

Hot compacted sheets were manufactured as follows. In order to produce a balanced final composite sheet, four layers of cloth were used for each sample, arranged balanced and symmetric about the centre $[0/90]_s$. If an interleaved film was to be used then this was put in between each layer of woven cloth. A thermocouple was placed between the central

layers at the edge of the woven stack and then the whole assembly was put between soft aluminium foil sheets and then between brass plates. The assembly was placed into a hot press set at the appropriate hot compaction temperature and a pressure of 700MPa was immediately applied. Once the assembly reached the compaction temperature, it was held for 5 minutes and then rapidly cooled: a typical cycle time was 12 minutes. Some results were already available for the plain weave cloth so samples were made as required: samples were made with both weave styles, with and without an interleaved film. Ideally, the film would have been made from the same polymer to that used for the melt spun Certran PE fibres. In this instance, that was not possible, so the film used was from Borealis FL5580 grade, ~ 15 μ m thick. Samples were made over a range of compaction temperatures from 138°C to 142°C. Mechanical tests carried out included the tensile modulus and strength (ASTM 638), the bending modulus and strength (ASTM 790) and the interlayer (peel) strength (ASTM 1846). The aim of these chosen tests was to determine an ‘optimum’ compaction temperature. At the optimum the compacted sample should have an adequate peel strength (which always increases with the temperature and hence the amount of matrix material produced) while retaining the original fibre modulus and strength which falls off with increasing compaction temperature.

Figure 2 shows a typical set of results, in this instance for the variation of the tensile modulus and peel strength with compaction temperature for the unidirectional weave style. Results are shown for compaction both with and without an interleaved film.

Figure 2: Tensile Modulus and peel strength vs compaction temperature for the unidirectional fibre cloth: with (■) and without (♦) and interleaved film.

The results show that there is the expected trade-off between modulus and peel strength as the compaction temperature is increased. If no interleaved film is used, it is difficult to find a temperature which gives both a high modulus and a high peel strength. A value of 8N/cm is considered an acceptable peel strength value, which required a temperature of 141°C, at which point the modulus has dropped to 15GPa. However, with the interleaved film, a

lower compaction temperature can be used (139°C), giving a higher peel strength of around 10N/cm and a tensile modulus of ~20GPa.

In light of these results, bending tests were carried out on samples made with the interleaved film for both weave styles. The tests were carried out at a large span/depth ratio (60:1) to reduce shear effects. Table 1 shows a comparison of the tensile and bending results measured for the ‘optimum’ interleaved film samples.

Weave Style	Test Type	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)
Uni + film	Flexural	22.2 ± 1.5	69.0 ± 5.8
Uni + film	Tensile	20	250
Plain + film	Flexural	9.43 ± 1.02	68.3 ± 0.9
Plain + film	Tensile	10	160

Table 1: A summary of the tensile and bending properties of hot compacted CERTRAN sheets.

The results show that the unidirectional weave style has twice the tensile modulus and almost twice the tensile strength of the plain weave samples. The tensile strength in bending shows a similar ratio, with unidirectional weave showing almost twice the value of the plain weave. The bending strength, however, is much lower in both cases and independent of weave style. This low bending strength is a result of the low shear modulus of oriented polyethylene: whereas the tensile modulus and strength are significantly increased with orientation the shear modulus is little changed.

THERMOFORMING EXPERIMENTS

a) stress-strain measurements at elevated temperature.

Figure 3: Tensile stress-strain curves at different temperatures

A key property of a single polymer composite is its ability to be thermoformed. The commercial success of hot compacted polypropylene (Curv™) is, in part, due to its thermoformability. In this programme we followed a similar strategy to that employed for polypropylene [14]. In the first instance, stress-strain curves were carried out on the hot compacted PE sheets at elevated temperatures below and up to the melting point as thermoforming, in general, involves some stretching of the material. The

results on Figure 4 are for the unidirectional weave style.

The results are interesting in that they are significantly different to those previously measured for polypropylene (PP). For PP, as the temperature was increased, the resistance to stretching was reduced, but importantly the strain to failure increased, making it an advantage to get as close as possible to the melting temperature, if the material is to be thermoformed as a homogeneous sheet. For polyethylene, however, the results shown in Figure 3 suggest that as the temperature is increased, the resistance to deformation is reduced and also the strain to failure. These results suggest an optimum thermoforming temperature between 100 and 110°C, where the resistance to deformation is reduced but the strain to failure is still reasonably high. As with the previous polypropylene studies, the testing rate had a much smaller effect on the stress-strain results: all the results shown in Figure 3 were tested at a crosshead speed of 20mm/min.

b) Thermoforming trials using a hemispherical tool.

Investigation of the thermoformability of the hot compacted PE sheets used a special rig manufactured for the previous studies on polypropylene [14], based on the original work of Hou [15]. The rig comprises a male and female hemispherical shape, matched for a sheet of 1mm thick, and the top male part incorporates a built in gripper plate (Figure 4). The whole rig is installed into an RDP servo mechanical test machine, in a temperature controlled oven.

Figure 4: Thermoforming rig: hemispherical mold.

To carry out a thermoforming test, the sheet is first placed above the female mould as shown in the Figure and left in the oven to reach the desired temperature (the bottom female mould also has a built in heater). The male mould is then brought down at a constant chosen closing speed. The gripper plate first contacts the sheet and as it descends the gripping force is increased by the springs. At a later point the male tool reaches the sample and thermoforming starts. The load during the thermoforming process is monitored and used to stop the machine once the mould is closed.

A range of tests were carried out, to assess the effect of closing speed (no effect over the range studied), gripping force and thermoforming temperature. Better formed hemispheres (with less internal debonding) were found to be formed

at a temperature of around 100°C, correlating well with the results of the elevated stress-strain tests reported in the previous section. It was also found, as with the previous PP studies, that forming was easier if the material was allowed to flow into the mould during

forming, by controlling the gripping force. Figure 5 shows a typical thermoformed hemisphere, in this case from the unidirectional weave style.

Figure 5: Thermoformed hemisphere (unidirectional weave style).

THERMOFORMING TRIALS – CENTRE CONSOLE BRACKET

The final part of this study was to use the knowledge obtained from the scientific studies described above to manufacture a demonstrator component. The part used was provided by one of the project partners, Visteon, and is a centre console bracket. The aim is to replace the metal bracket with an alternative material in order to reduce weight while retaining performance. Figure 6 shows the metal bracket, which is 150mm long and weights 115g.

Figure 6: Visteon centre console bracket.

The tool used to manufacture this metal component was kindly loaned to the project by Visteon. The tool was installed in the RDP servo-mechanical test machine but was too large this time to be installed in the temperature controlled oven. The tool was heated to a suitable temperature using a hot air gun (40°C was typical) and the sheet was preheated in the oven. Both the elevated stress-strain tests, and the hemispherical moulding trials, suggested an optimum forming temperature of 100°C. The sheet to be formed was therefore

heated to 120°C, such that it would be at the required temperature after transferring to the console bracket tool. Figure 7 shows a formed sample in the fully closed tool.

Figure 7: Console bracket tool with formed sample

The tool was closed at a fast speed of 100mm/min until a small compressive load was registered. The final 2mm was carried out at a slow speed of 1mm/min until a force of 10kN was reached. The tool was designed for forming a 2mm thick sheet.

Figure 8: Formed console brackets from hot compacted PE sheet: plain weave

Figure 8 shows typical formed console brackets from, in this instance, the plain weave samples. The weight of a 2mm thick bracket was 20g, which compares very favourably with the weight of the metal bracket of 115g. It is seen that the brackets were successfully formed using the conditions established from above. Tests are currently underway to assess the mechanical properties of the brackets against the Visteon specification for this part. Long term exposure tests are in progress at both low and elevated temperatures, as well as loading tests.

CONCLUSIONS

- A unidirectional weave style gives twice the sheet stiffness and strength compared to a plain weave.
- The flexural strength is much lower than the tensile strength and independent of weave style.
- The best thermoforming temperature is 100°C. At higher temperatures, the resistance to forming decreases, but so does the strain to failure.
- A demonstrator component was successfully thermoformed using matched metal tooling from hot compacted PE sheet. The single polyethylene composite part had a weight five times less than the equivalent metal part.

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